

BOOST D4.2: Progress with establishing a TRE on JASMIN

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Introduction

The original plan for the BOOST project included work to explore the practicalities of establishing a functional Trusted Research Environment (TRE) on JASMIN to allow access to environmental data alongside data of a sensitive nature. The initial planning of the work was focused on the technical aspects of implementing a suitable environment.

This work progressed alongside efforts in other projects, in particular DARE UK (<https://dareuk.org.uk/>), to establish and refine an agreed framework for operation of TREs that enables operators to certify that their TRE is compliant with the expected standards. As a result of this work, the “Five Safes” framework (Figure 1) has emerged as the accepted standard for an environment to be deemed a compliant TRE.

Safe data: data is treated to protect any confidentiality concerns.

Safe projects: research projects are approved by data owners for the public good.

Safe people: researchers are trained and authorised to use data safely.

Safe settings: a SecureLab environment prevents unauthorised use.

Safe outputs: screened and approved outputs that are non-disclosive.

Figure 1: The “Five Safes” framework

The technical implementation of the environment falls primarily under the “Safe settings” item, and the safeguards represented by the Five Safes framework extend well beyond this to cover the human and project safeguards.

Progress

The NERC Digital Solutions Programme (DSP) team evaluated a number of options for implementation of a secure environment on JASMIN, before selecting the e-Lab Digital Workbench solution (<https://assets.bmh.manchester.ac.uk/diids/elab/homepage/index.html>) developed at Manchester University. This solution offers a customizable and extensible implementation of a secure data environment, suitable for deployment on a variety of platforms.

The DSP team successfully implemented a version of e-Lab on JASMIN, and engaged in a series of discussions with the JASMIN team about practicalities and resources. The work demonstrated the feasibility of running a technically functioning TRE on JASMIN.

Whilst the technical implementation of a secure environment was successful, progress with building on this to develop a Five Safes compliant TRE raised some challenges.

Firstly, the non-technical requirements of the Five Safes framework are very labour-intensive, and require involvement of the target user community. For example, certification of safe researchers to access the environment requires community insight, and assurance of safe outputs requires manual output checking by an expert in assessing whether outputs are non-disclosive. These activities are typically carried out manually, requiring investment of significant staff time. These aspects of the Five Safes could therefore not practically be tackled by either the DSP or JASMIN teams.

Secondly, there has been a proliferation of TREs within the DARE UK community, and discussion with researchers involved with these highlighted that those working with sensitive data are unlikely to be persuaded to move their data into a different TRE. This is partly because of familiarity with their current TRE and the overhead in moving to a new environment, and partly because of concerns about the security of any new TRE. Furthermore, members of the community expressed doubt about the level of confidence that could be built in a TRE operated as part of a research council activity on widely used digital research infrastructure. In this context, it is highly unlikely that other communities could be persuaded to devote scarce resources to supporting a TRE on JASMIN.

These two points taken together pose a significant barrier to developing the technically functioning TRE on JASMIN into a Five Safes compliant TRE.

Prospects

Whilst the dialogue with the DARE UK community has highlighted some barriers to pursuing the original plan to establish a compliant TRE on JASMIN, it has also helped to identify some potential options for addressing the underlying need to bring together environmental and sensitive data.

In consequence, the emphasis for this has moved away from establishing an additional TRE, in favour of exploring options to enable access to environmental data within, or from, existing TREs operated by others.

Several projects funded through DARE UK are experimenting with federation of TREs at various levels to enable sharing of data between different environments. These projects are anticipated to provide some insight into effective mechanisms for federating data sources, which should provide useful guidance to assist with developing approaches to enabling access to the environmental data.

Alongside this, the UKRI NetworkPlus on National Federated Compute Services will develop a roadmap for federation of digital research infrastructures, which will identify possible mechanisms for enabling federated access to data. These mechanisms may also provide useful options for enabling TRE access to environmental access.

FRIDGE Project

[The Fridge project](#) aims to deliver a portable, cross-platform SATRE and NHS standards compliant Trusted Research Environment (TRE) into production on AIRR, the UK's national AI research supercomputing platform. This will provide the ability to strongly isolate parts of the AIRR system for an individual project that uses sensitive data, so that this data can only be accessed by approved researchers and can be administered under the information governance regime approved for the project.

The software and associated legal agreements and policies for systems like AIRR to run the FRIDGE TRE will be published openly for others to easily reuse, either to deploy their sensitive data projects to the AIRR platform or to enable other supercomputers to support hosting such projects in TREs on their systems. We anticipate the results of the project could have strong implications for JASMIN and other UKRI Data Analysis platforms as such this is a project whose results we intend to track post project.

Further Work with DARE UK and BOOST

Our work with Digital Solutions led to follow discussion with both with digital solution on work package 2 but also with DARE UK. We also held dedicated meetings with both Digital Solutions and DARE UK to have conversations about the emergency complexities of establishing TREs, how they could benefit from workflows and how emerging technologies such as RO-Crates could facilitate this.

They were also about to share the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint v2.2 <https://zenodo.org/records/14192786> for us to consider its implications for environmental data archives. It talks to overall federation for TREs. Section 5.3 looks at some of the current data standards recommended by ONS (and UK Gov generally) which could impact potential format conversion that environmental archives could consider.

We were also given the recent Wellcome/ESRC technical White Paper submission competition on “what is the National Data Library” <https://zenodo.org/records/14329831>. Which has stimulated dialogue into how we as a data centre can fit into a federated National Data Library.

Joint DARE UK/ BOOST Workshop

As we felt it was important for the Environmental Data Service centres, scientific community and other members of the Data Analysis Platform working group to continue discussions on how we can improve the interoperability of our data and platforms. We had initially planned to hold the workshop on the 20th March 2025, however due many projects closing at the end of March we decided to reschedule to the 9th May 2025.

The aims of the workshop are as follows:

1. To gain a better understanding of what health researcher need in terms of environmental data
2. To gain a better understanding of the capacity of Health TREs
 - a. Volumes of environmental data they can accommodate
 - b. Data transfer rates that can be handled
 - c. Tools/software used by and flexibility to install new tools/software on Health TREs
3. Discuss how EDS and other data centre can promote their data holdings to health researchers
4. Discuss what sort workflows TRE's might benefit from .The kinds of data transformation that health researchers might benefit from for example rescaling, format conversions and compression
5. Dare UK to inform attendees on the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint, vision for a “National Data Library” and inform us of relevant projects that the NERC community can engage with.

Summary

The overall direction of the work to enable access to environmental data alongside data of a sensitive nature has evolved during the course of the BOOST work, as a result of learning through experimentation, and dialogue with other communities. As a consequence, we are now in the position where we have a much clearer view of the most likely route to success, and the on-going conversations around this have the potential to lead to practical progress over the coming year.